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Research Article

A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE FREQUENCY OF FORDYCE'S GRANULES WITH RESPECT TO GENDER, AGE AND SITE OF SPOTS

¹Dr Hafsah Sherwani, ²Dr Hafsa Shoaib, ³Dr Mishal Rehman

¹Allied Hospital Faisalabad

²Govt Mian Munshi DHQ 1 Teaching Hospital

³Dental Surgeon, Trauma Centre THQ Hospital Kallar Kahar

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Abstract:

Objective: The objective of this research was to determine the frequency of Fordyce's granules among those patients who visited Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

Patients and Methods: This cross-sectional research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from October 2017 to May 2018 on a total of 257 patients. In the total population, the males were 176 and females were 81. The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of 17 years to 85 years. Clinical assessment was carried out for all the patients. Research commenced after the informed written consent of the patients and ethical review permission of the institution.

Results: Among 257 patients, 131 presented the occurrence of Fordyce's granules at various oral cavity sites. Males were more affected than females in terms of Fordyce's granules presence (57% Versus 37%). All those who were more than twenty years of age presented a higher incidence of the presence of Fordyce's granules. Males presented higher Fordyce's granules occurrences in the third and fourth decade of their age; whereas, females were more involved in the fourth and fifth decade of their age. The most common site of Fordyce's granules was Buccal mucosa which was found among 61% patients along with another site such as upper lip, lower lip, retromolar area, gingiva and vermilion border.

Conclusion: Most common site of Fordyce's granules was Buccal mucosa along with another site such as upper lip, lower lip, retromolar area, gingiva and vermilion border. There was a significant difference among females and males in terms of Fordyce's granules occurrence for both gender and age.

Keywords: Ectopic Sebaceous Glands, White Patch, Fordyce's Granules, Gingiva, Vermilion Border, Retromolar Area, Lower Lip, Upper Lip, Buccal Mucosa.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Hafsah Sherwani,
Allied Hospital Faisalabad

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Fordyce's granules are commonly found at oral cavity site which is actually ectopic sebaceous glands in the form of small, raised, painless, white or yellowish spots (1 to 3 mm) in diameter [1]. Most repeated site for Fordyce's granules occurrence is lips and vermilion border and lips as shown in Figure [2]. Another common site is buccal mucosa specifically inside the retromolar and commissures region as shown in Figure. Their appearance is also observable on the penis shaft, scrotum and labia [1].

Controversies also prevail in the occurrence of Fordyce's granules occurrence in the oral cavity [1]. Estimates suggest that eighty percent patients have Fordyce's spots in the oral cavity; whereas, a large number of granules are rare. Normally children do not present such signs and its appearance is found at a later stage in adulthood from twenty years and onwards with different age and gender-wise occurrence [2]. Few studies also suggest its occurrence at an early stage of adulthood or in the middle of adulthood [3]. Their prominence in males is also suggested [2]. On the contrary, different authors do not consider the difference between males and females that much significant [4]. The relevance of genetic association is etiologically connected with Fordyce's granules [3]. Similarly, an idiopathic aetiology is also suggested in these granules; whereas, no such association has been established with any other illness or disease [5]. It is just a cosmetic concern [5]. Few authors are of the view that some rheumatic disorders are also correlated with Fordyce's spots [6].

Different clinical features are sufficient to indicate the presence of Fordyce's spots through histopathological assessment in an easy way [7]. Whereas, a benign outcome, among those patients who present the prominent and increased appearance of Fordyce spots, should seek proper treatment. Oral isotretinoin and CO₂ laser ablation are helpful management strategies [8]. Significant side effects and poor treatment outcomes have been reported for 5-aminolevulinic acid (ALA) photodynamic treatment approach [9]. Whereas, gentle curettage and electrodesiccation are safe, easily available and well-tolerated modalities available for management of Fordyce spots [10].

Even in rising awareness, most of the clinicians consider the prevalence of Fordyce's spots with significant differences. Therefore, the objective of our research was to determine the frequency of Fordyce's granules among patients visiting the hospital.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from October 2017 to May 2018 on a total of 257 patients. In the total population, the males were 176 and females were 81. The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of 17 years to 85 years. Clinical assessment was carried out for all the patients. Research commenced after the informed written consent of the patients and ethical review permission of the institution. A single examiner carried out all the evaluations by using mouth mirror in the presence of suitable illuminated setting. Clinical assessment was carried on different anatomic sites such as buccal mucosa, upper lips, lower lips, retromolar area, vermilion border and gingiva for the presence of Fordyce's granules. We analyzed the outcomes on SPSS software and Chi-Square test (P-Value < 0.05).

RESULTS:

Among 257 patients, 131 presented the occurrence of Fordyce's granules at various oral cavity sites. Males were more affected than females in terms of Fordyce's granules presence (57% Versus 37%). All those who were more than twenty years of age presented a higher incidence of the presence of Fordyce's granules. Males presented higher Fordyce's granules occurrences in the third and fourth decade of their age; whereas, females were more involved in the fourth and fifth decade of their age. The most common site of Fordyce's granules was Buccal mucosa which was found among 61% patients along with another site such as upper lip, lower lip, retromolar area, gingiva and vermilion border. The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of 17 years to 85 years with a mean age of 42.2 years. Detailed outcomes have been shown in the given tabular and graphical data.

Table – I shows the comparison of patients with and without Fordyce's granules with respect to age and gender among total 176 males and 81 females.

Table – I: Comparison of Patients with and without Fordyce’s granules with respect to Age and Gender

Gender/ Age		Patients with Fordyce’s granules		Patients without Fordyce’s granules		P-Value
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Gender	Male (176)	101	57	75	42	0.002
	Female (81)	30	37	51	62	
Age	Under 20 Years (55)	8	14	47	85	
	Above 20 Years (202)	123	60	79	39	

Table – II shows the occurrence of Fordyce's Granules with respect to site unilaterally and bilaterally.

Table – II: Stratification of Different Sites

Sites		Fordyce's granules	
		Total	Distribution
Upper Lip	Unilateral	27	18
	Bilateral		9
Lower Lip	Unilateral	8	6
	Bilateral		2
Buccal Mucosa	Unilateral	80	36
	Bilateral		44
Vermilion Border	Unilateral	2	1
	Bilateral		1
Retromolar Area	Unilateral	13	9
	Bilateral		4
Gingiva	Unilateral	1	1
	Bilateral		0

Table – III: Gender and Age Distribution

Age (Years)	Male	Female
0 to 9	0	0
10 to 19	5	1
20 to 29	16	6
30 to 39	23	6
40 to 49	23	7
50 to 59	18	7
60 to 69	13	5
Above 70	0	1

Figure: Multiple yellowish (pin sized) spots on buccal mucosa and upper lip

DISCUSSION:

Fordyce's granules are commonly found at oral cavity site which is actually ectopic sebaceous glands in the form of small, raised, painless, white or yellowish spots; most repeated site for Fordyce's granules occurrence is lips and vermillion border and lips; another common site is buccal mucosa specifically inside retromolar and commissures region [11]. Their appearance is also observable on penis shaft, scrotum and labia [11].

We reported the occurrence of Fordyce's granules (61%) on the site of buccal mucosa followed by upper

lip (20%), retromolar area (10%), lower lip (6%), vermillion border (1.5%) and gingiva (0.76%). Previous research outcomes report about the non-visibility of Fordyce's granules among children which appear in the age of three years after that in the puberty and adulthood it becomes more visible with an increased and prominent occurrence among males [2, 3]. In the same way, our research reported a predominance of Fordyce's granules among males in the third and fourth decade of age; whereas, a higher prevalence is reported among females in the fourth and fifth decade of age. There is no association of

Fordyce's granules with any illness, disease or infection; it appears as an outcome of natural process on the body [5]. Normally, there is no association between the hair follicle and sebaceous glands. They are more visual among greasy skins and among people who present rheumatic disorders [6]. No biopsy is carried out for oral Fordyce's granules due to their clinical rapid diagnosis. Fordyce's granules require no treatment unless there are cosmetic concerns. Oral isotretinoin and CO² laser ablation are helpful management strategies. A number of clinicians take it as a normal physiological phenomenon and suggest no traditional treatment [12].

CONCLUSION:

The most common site of Fordyce's granules was Buccal mucosa along with another site such as upper lip, lower lip, retromolar area, gingiva and vermilion border. There was a significant difference among females and males in terms of Fordyce's granules occurrence for both gender and age.

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